

THEORETICAL AND METHODOLOGICAL ISSUES OF EXPRESSIVE READING. HISTORICAL DEVELOPMENT OF EXPRESSIVE READING

¹Qosimova A.F., ²Bomurodova G.J.

¹Doctoral student of Tashkent State Pedagogical University named after Nizami

²Teacher at Tashkent State Pedagogical University named after Nizami, Department of "Methods of Teaching Native Language in Primary Education"

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Abstract. *This article presents the historical development path of teaching expressive reading to students, the scholars who conducted research in this field, and their thoughts and opinions.*

Keywords: *expressive reading, theory, methodology, development of reading, developmental path, historical development, feedback.*

It is known that the history of the methodology of expressive reading began to develop in our country from the first half of the 19th century. In his book "Expressive Reading," Russian scholar Professor N.I. Kwartsov stated the following: "Although the ideas and discussions about expressive reading began to be introduced into our country's schools as early as the 1830s, they were officially and widely accepted by the government only in the late 19th century."

Many Russian scholars have conducted research on issues related to the methodology of expressive reading. Among them, Russian methodologists such as F.I. Buslaev, N.Ya. Stoyunin, V.P. Ostrogorskiy, V.I. Vodovozov, V.P. Sheremetskiy, and N.F. Bunakov expressed a number of relevant opinions and considerations about the teaching methodology of language and literature, including expressive reading.

In the book "Expressive Reading" of 1885 V.P. Ostrogorskiy outlined the theoretical aspects of teaching expressive reading, including voice, breath control, pronunciation, stress, intonation, pauses, and their significance in the process of expressive reading. He has earned a unique place in the history of literature teaching methodology as one of the founders of expressive reading methodology in Russia.

Professor M.A. Ribnikova, in her book "Essays on the Methodology of Literary Reading," and academician B.B. Golubkov, in his book "Methodology of Teaching Literature," emphasized the necessity of teaching expressive reading in schools and outlined the methods and tools that could be used for reading literary works expressively. "One of the common defects in children's speech," M.A. Ribnikova pointed out, "is primarily in pronunciation, as children are unable to speak with a loud and bright voice. This issue must be addressed during primary education. If the primary education system works comprehensively and systematically on making students' speech expressive, we could assign even more complex tasks to them when they reach higher grades".

Russian methodologist scholars such as N.I. Kwartsov, E.V. Yazovitskiy, G.N. Firsov, L.A. Gorbushina, E.D. Dmitrieva, I.Ya. Blinov, and a number of other specialists made significant contributions to the development of this field with their works on expressive reading methodology.

Until 1917, no special methodological manual on expressive reading had been created in Uzbekistan. In the old schools of this period, classical poems written by poets like Navoi,

Bedil, Khoja Khafiz, and Fuzuli in the aruz meter were taught in their original form. The teachers did not work on the content of the poems or explain them; instead, they simply made students memorize them blindly.

Regarding the teaching of literature in the old-style schools and the teaching of expressive reading as a subject, Sadridin Aini said the following:

"Literature was not taught as a subject. However, those interested in literature would engage in it to the best of their knowledge. But in the Mir Arab madrasah, which had more than 300 students and 'graduated' mullahs, I did not meet anyone who talked about poetry and literature. My brother's companions, Mulla Hamid from Gijduvan and Zayniddin Khoja from Mirkulol, memorized various lyrical ghazals and sang them in different styles of Shashmaqom and folk tunes. But these amateur singers, as well as their listeners, paid no attention to the content of these ghazals, nor did they care whether they were reading them in a correct or incorrect form. The reason was that they themselves did not distinguish between correct and incorrect interpretations of these ghazals".

In 1917, literary scholars such as H.H. Niyazi, A. Avloni, S. Aini, and A. Shukuri encouraged the people of Uzbekistan toward development and spiritual-educational growth. They established new schools for the younger generation and created various textbooks. They also began to pay special attention to cultivating students' skills in reading literary works expressively. H.H. Niyazi, in textbooks like "Yengil Adabiyot" ("Light Literature"), "O'qish Kitobi" ("Reading Book"), and "Qiroat Kitobi" ("Reading Book"), provided the first general and specific guidelines on expressive and explanatory reading methodology in Uzbekistan. Niyazi was against mere rote memorization in teaching literature and recommended methods to foster students' interest in books and reading. He wrote, "If the teacher had drawn attention to and taught effective methods... students would increase by millions, not just thousands, year after year."

In 1934, Professor A. Saadiy published the first methodological manual titled "Main Issues of the Methodology of Teaching Literature in Secondary Schools". This manual discussed teaching elementary school students by integrating education with upbringing. It also addressed teaching students to read expressively, highlighting existing shortcomings in this area. For example, it was noted that "Teacher's weakness in fully equipping students with artistic and literary techniques was a major shortcoming". The author continues: "In literature, language is the primary material, and when we talk about artistic and literary techniques, it first and foremost involves mastering the language."

In 1952, S. Dolimov and H. Ubaydullayev created the manual "Methodology of Literary Reading". This manual contained valuable thoughts and observations on expressive reading. It covered various aspects such as reading poems in classroom, the characteristics of expressive reading, types of expressive reading lessons, and tools like individual reading, chorus reading, role-play reading, intonation, pauses, emphasis, reading speed, diction, and storytelling techniques. The manual also highlighted the importance of expressive reading lessons in the overall curriculum and how it contributed to students' ability to analyze and synthesize literary works.

Specialized methodological manuals on expressive reading began to be created mainly after the 1960s in Uzbekistan. In 1968, K. Jurayev published "Expressive Reading and Storytelling," and in 1973, S. Inomkhodjaev published "Fundamentals of Artistic Reading". K. Jurayev's work became a very useful book for primary school teachers, while the book aimed to

teach students aesthetic education through the expressive reading of Russian literature samples. S. Inomkhodjaev's book focused primarily on stage speech and the development of acting skills.

In conclusion, one of the most important tasks of both primary and literature teachers is to improve the quality of students' knowledge, develop their communicative abilities, and nurture their speech competencies. It is also crucial to expand students' scientific worldview by linking reading methods with real life. Through expressive reading, it is necessary to cultivate students' artistic worldview and aesthetic appreciation. These issues are among the most relevant topics today.

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